

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDIES OF CARMINIC ACID COMPLEXES

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Carminic acid complexes with Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Th^{4+} , and Zr^{4+} have been studied spectrophotometrically, when these (including carminic acid) are present in comparable low concentrations of 10^{-4} mole/litre at room temperature. While copper and lead form stable complexes in water and acid solutions, the complexes and the acid are unstable in alkaline solutions. Thorium probably forms a salt but not a complex, and zirconium does not appear to react under these conditions.

The capacity of carminic acid to form a complex with many different cations has been studied by many workers (Welcher, "Organic Anal. Reagents", Vol. IV, p. 443, D. Van Nostrand Publication, 1955). Carminic acid contains the same reactive groups as other hydroxyquinone dyes. Since it contains in addition a carboxyl group, which may function as a part of reactive structure, it has been thought proper to study its complexing properties under acid, neutral, and alkaline conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Complexes of Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Th^{4+} , and Zr^{4+} were studied spectrophotometrically. Carminic acid in water solution has a deep red colour and is yellow to violet in acid solutions. The absorption spectra are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. In alkaline medium, the colour obtained immediately is deep purple, which fades on standing. λ_{max} and the associated molecular extinction coefficients for carminic acid are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Medium.	λ_{max} .	pH.	ϵ .	Colour.
Water	500	3.4	6,800	Stable
$\text{HCl } 2 \times 10^{-2}$	490-500	2.0	5,800	-
$\text{NaOH } 1 \times 10^{-4}$	540	6.2	3,450	Unstable
$\text{NH}_4\text{Cl } 1 \times 10^{-3}$	540		7,800	-

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Solutions of analytical grades of CuSO_4 , $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$, and technical grade of zirconium nitrate and BDH carminic acid were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amounts in

water to get the concentrated solution and diluting them to furnish the concentrations in the range of 10^{-4} mole/litre. Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 colorimeter was used for measurements of optical densities with 1 cm cuvettes.

Nature of Complexes.—For a set of experiments, mixtures containing varying concentrations of metallic ions and carminic acid, either in water or in HCl or NaOH, were prepared and the optical density in each case was measured in the range of 400-600 $m\mu$. The absorption spectra in water and HCl are reproduced in Figs. 1 and 2. In the presence of alkalis, wherever the colour was unstable, optical densities immediately after mixing were noted and compared (Table II).

TABLE II
Carminic acid = 1×10^{-4} mole/litre = C.

Ratio C : M.	λ_{max} .	O.D.	Remarks.
			M = Copper sulphate.
1:1	535 $m\mu$	0.355	NaOH $\times 10^{-2}$. Colour purple, unstable
1:0.6	540	0.355	NaOH $\times 10^{-2}$. Colour purple, unstable
			M = Thorium nitrate
1:1	570	0.320	NaOH $\times 10^{-2}$. Blue, stable
			M = Lead nitrate.
1:1	545	0.423	NaOH $\times 10^{-2}$. Blue-purple, unstable

Finally Job's method (*Ann. chim.*, 1928 x, 9, 113) of continued variation was also applied to ascertain the molar composition of the metallic complexes.

DISCUSSION

From Figs. 1 and 2 it would be seen that copper and lead form complexes in water as in HCl. The increasing acidity has very slight effect on the absorption of complexes. The molar ratios for the complexes would appear to be 1 of carminic acid to 0.5 of the metal at pH 1.0 to 3.8 by using Job's method (Fig. 3). From Figs. 1 and 2 it would appear that the maximum absorption wave length for the complexes and for the acid alone are practically the same, but these differ in their molar absorbance index. After making an allowance for the free acid absorbance, the optical densities at the maximum absorbance wave lengths for the complexes were plotted against the increasing concentrations of the metal ions (Fig. 3) to obtain the composition ratio of the complexes. The molar ratio for lead complex has been reported to be the same by Pavelka (cf. Welcher, *loc. cit.*), and the probable structure as given to the complex is as shown below.

Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Th^{4+} are reported to form purple precipitates, which dissolve on addition of HCl ("Reagents for Qualitative Inorganic Analysis", edited by Wengar and Duckert, Elsevier Publishing Co., 1948, p. 150).

FIG. 3

The effect of alkalis on the colour of the complexes is of particular interest. It has been noticed that the colour of copper and lead complexes disappears on their addition. The stronger the alkalis, quicker is the fading, which is also the case when only carminic acid is taken. The colour of the thorium solution, however, was found to remain unaffected by addition of alkalis even when other cations were present. But the absorption maxima shift with the changing concentrations of thorium. (Table III) when the concentration of carminic acid and pH (6.2) are kept the same.

TABLE III

Th conc. $\times 10^{-4}$	0.19	0.12	0.06	0.251	0.503	0.603	1.02	1.52	2.29
λ_{max} (m μ)	550	510	510	560	570	570	570	575	580

Now this difference of the behaviour of thorium cation on the one hand and of copper or lead cations on the other leads us to believe that lead and copper form complexes, structures of which would be like the one shown elsewhere, and that while reaction with thorium would be different, it does not form a complex but probably forms a salt with carminic acid. The thorium salt of carminic acid remains stable in presence of alkalis while the copper and lead complexes are unstable in their presence. The fading of colour of carminic acid alone (10^{-4} mole/litre) with NaOH (10^{-3} mole/litre) could be followed spectrophotometrically at room temperature. Average value on the first order reaction constant k was found to be 6.8×10^{-3} mole per min. Similarly the kinetics of the copper complex colour fading, under identical conditions, provide the value of the first order constant $k = 1.5 \times 10^{-2}$ mole min^{-1} . It would thus appear that the mechanism for

these would be the same. In the case of thorium, if it forms a true salt and not a co-ordination complex, it will remain unaffected on addition of alkalies as both the oxygen atoms of the two carbonyl groups are not co-ordinated; the colour might however, disappear if excess of alkali is used so that thorium hydroxide so obtained may absorb the dye as was found by Goto (*Chem. Abs.*, 1941, 35, 1720) in case of cochineal, which contains a high percentage of carminic acid.

Mixtures of Cations.—When a mixture of copper and thorium is taken, the O.D. measurements show that absorption is entirely due to copper complex; thorium does not interfere at all pH ranges.

Reaction with Zirconium.—Although reported as a spot test by Feigl ("Spot Test", p. 157, 1947) the reaction with zirconium at such low concentrations of carminic acid does not appear to take place in any medium at room temperature.

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